

Improving Treatment Adherence for HBV and HCV Patients through Counselling and Education: A Case Study at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa

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Abstract

Keywords: Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C, patient adherence, counselling, health education, South Africa

Introduction: This study investigates the potential of counselling and health education strategies to improve treatment adherence among HBV and HCV patients at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa; the broad objectives were to explore the experiences of HBV and HCV patients with counselling and education by healthcare professionals regarding knowledge and awareness, format of instructions, and relevance of information provision to patients' health problems at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa.

Methods: The study adopted a qualitative approach using a non-probability/purposive sampling technique. Qualitative data was collected from HBV and HCV patients until data saturation was reached at eighteen through in-depth interviews with patients who consented and availed themselves of the study.

Findings: Most participants indicated they needed to be made aware of counselling and education programmes and the format of information dissemination. However, a few participants indicated that they are aware of counselling and education provided by health professionals at the hospital through direct counselling.

Conclusion and implications: Patient counselling and education can significantly improve treatment adherence for patients, as well as social and psychological coping with the treatment's challenges. Findings would contribute to evidence-based strategies for addressing challenges with lack of knowledge, improving understanding of factors influencing information use behaviour of HBV and HCV patients regarding counselling and education to create awareness for medication adherence and decision making.

Introduction:

Debates about the spread of hepatitis B and C as a silent killer disease in developed and developing countries worldwide have gained extensive discussions for over seven decades (WHO, 2024). Current data show that the burden is increasing in many countries in Africa and sub-regions (WHO, 2024). The critical importance of imparting comprehensive education to patients about Hepatitis B (HBV) and Hepatitis C (HCV) to ensure a better understanding of the mode of transmission, potential complications, and the severe damage caused to the liver, such as cirrhosis and liver cancer have been highlighted in several studies (Obeagu & Obeagu, 2024; Hayat et al., 2018; Dunn & Conard, 2018; Rantucci, 2007). Research shows that over 4.5 million premature deaths could be avoided in developing countries by 2030 through vaccination, diagnostic tests, medicines and education campaigns (WHO, 2024). HBV and HCV are primarily transmitted through blood and bodily fluids, and patients need to be informed of the associated transmission risks and the importance of adopting preventive measures (WHO, 2024).

Counselling can provide emotional support to patients and assist them in managing the psychological impact of the disease. Counselling is essential for HBV and HCV patients to enable them cope with the emotional challenges and to improve their overall quality of life. The epidemic nature of HBV and HCV require the need for clear, patient-centred education and counselling, which is an effective way to provide crucial emotional support for HBV and HCV patients. Patients can empower themselves with knowledge and understanding of their health conditions, modes of transmission, prevention, treatment options, and effective ways to manage their health (Schulz & Nakamoto, 2013). Counselling and education can give

patients the tools to feel more in control of their health, make informed decisions, adhere to treatment plans, and adopt a proactive approach to managing their condition (Wittink & Oosterhaven, 2018). By learning how to prevent the spread of the virus to others and minimising the impact of the disease on family, friends, and the wider community, patients can make a meaningful contribution to public health (Ali & Alharbi, 2020).

Patient education can provide patients with reliable information about their health conditions, treatment plans, medications, and self-management strategies (Falvo, 2010). Through education, patients can dismiss myths and misconceptions, which can help reduce stigma and increase social support (Obeagu & Obeagu, 2024). Patients' education aims to equip them with the knowledge and skills to be actively manage their own healthcare.

Patient Education is essential for several reasons, such as improving patients' health outcomes (Falvo, 2010). Studies consistently show that patients who understand their health conditions and treatments have better outcomes (Dunn & Conard, 2018; Schapira et al., 2017; Manning & Kripalani, 2007) in terms of better adherence to medication schedules, increased chances of lifestyle changes, making more informed decisions about treatment options, having lower chances of complications, improved patient-provider relationship in terms of trust and collaboration, comfortable, a sense of control over their health and increased level of self-efficacy and ability to manage their conditions (Lambert et al., 2001). Healthcare providers must present health information about patients' illnesses in an understandable way by considering their educational background and health literacy level (Murray et al., 20, Street et al., 2009). Patients' education could be provided using different formats for instructions. These may include verbal explanations or instructions and

discussion methods with doctors, nurses, pharmacists, and other healthcare providers. Patients' education could also be provided using written materials such as brochures, pamphlets, online resources, and patient portals with condition-specific information. Other instruction formats could include visual aids: Diagrams, videos, and interactive demonstrations. Sometimes, the format of information dissemination may include group classes or workshops during which the instructors or facilitators could cover topics such as disease management, medication use, and lifestyle changes. In a digital age, the mode of instruction for patient education may involve using technology-based tools such as apps, websites, and telehealth portals for information and support.

Patient counselling involves educating patients about their medications. It is a vital part of healthcare where a healthcare professional provides essential information such as advice and support to patients about their medications (Rantucci, 2007). Counselling can motivate patients to seek early diagnosis, testing, screening, treatment, and prevention of disease progression and severe complications. Taking a constructive approach and empowering patients to manage their health is essential. By doing so, we can help patients build resilience and make informed choices that lead to better health outcomes. Patients must improve their knowledge and understanding of their health conditions, modes of transmission, prevention, treatment options, and effective ways to manage their health (Alhumaid et al., 2021). Counselling and education help patients feel more in control of their health, make informed decisions, adhere to treatment plans, and adopt proactive lifestyle changes to manage their condition. There is no room for error when preventing the spread of the virus to others and minimising the impact of the disease on family, friends, and the wider community.

This study investigates HBV and HCV patients in a selected tertiary health institution in South Africa. The hospital provides treatment for HBV and HCV patients. Besides, the hospital's proximity allowed the researcher to collect qualitative data from HBV and HCV patients. The study envisaged that findings could bridge the information gap in the existing literature exploring the experiences of HBV and HCV patients with counselling and education by healthcare professionals regarding knowledge and awareness, the format of instructions, and the relevance of information provision to patients' health problems at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa.

This study contributes to the body of knowledge by improving the understanding of factors influencing the information use behaviour of HBV and HCV patients regarding counselling and education to create awareness of the risks of the disease, medication adherence, and decision-making. User experiences are an essential aspect of information science related to this study. Understanding how patients interact with and respond to counselling and education interventions can provide insights into the user experience design of healthcare information systems. The study added knowledge informing the development of effective patients-centred interventions for improving treatment and medication adherence by HBV and HCV patients in South Africa, including sub-Saharan African regions. Besides, the hospital's proximity allowed the researcher to collect qualitative data from HBV and HCV patients.

Statement of the Problems

Discussions about the burden of hepatitis B and C in developed and developing countries worldwide have gained widespread discussions for over seven decades (WHO, 2024). Hepatitis B and C pose significant

public health threats, yet patients often lack the knowledge and support from counselling and education programs to manage their condition effectively. Lack of knowledge leaves individuals less likely to adhere to treatment regimens and more vulnerable to complications. An estimated 4.5 million premature deaths are expected to be prevented in low- and middle-income countries by 2030 through vaccination, diagnostic tests, medicines and education campaigns (WHO, 2024). Health education and counselling are critical to support the prevention of HBV and HCV transmitted through blood and bodily fluids and various modes of transmission

Patients living with hepatitis B and C require tailored counselling and education strategies that address their specific knowledge gaps, psychological needs, and the unique challenges of their treatment journey. A lack of such targeted support contributes to poor treatment adherence and suboptimal health outcomes. The importance of comprehensive education provision to patients about the awareness of HBV and HCV has been emphasised to ensure a better understanding of the mode of transmission, potential complications, and the severe damage caused to the liver, such as cirrhosis and liver cancer (Obeagu & Obeagu, 2024; Hayat et al., 2018; Dunn & Conard, 2018; Rantucci, 2007).

This study explores the experiences of HBV and HCV patients with counselling and education by healthcare professionals regarding knowledge and awareness, the format of instructions, and the relevance of information provision to patients' health problems at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. From a social science point of view, individuals' health-related behaviours are influenced by their perceptions of susceptibility to a health threat. At the same time, the illness's severity, the treatment's perceived benefits, and barriers to adhering to treatment recommendations (Fava

et al., 2023; DiMatteo et al., 2007). Understand how counselling and education interventions enhance patients' confidence in their ability to adhere to treatment regimens and how observational learning from peers or healthcare providers can positively influence adherence behaviours (Battaglioli-DeNero, 2007). Hence, this study improves treatment adherence for HBV and HCV patients through counselling and education in information science. It advances understanding of how information is utilised, managed, and disseminated in healthcare contexts to improve treatment adherence and patient outcomes.

Although counselling and education intervention's critical role is to increase individual patients' self-efficacy and improve treatment adherence, studies focusing on education and counselling for patients' awareness have not been sufficiently investigated. Research has shown that patients with HBV and HCV often lack knowledge about transmission, disease progression, and treatment options (Hasan et al., 2018; Ha & Timmerman, 2018; Mukherjee et al., 2017; Ganczak et al., 2016)—a clear, patient-centred education tailored to the individual's unique needs and circumstances. Patients must understand the disease, including its potential complications, and the available treatment options. Awareness of the risk factors is essential because HBV and HCV carry a significant stigma, leading to feelings of shame and isolation among patients, predominantly female patients (Benek-Higgins et al., 2008). It is unclear whether patients are provided with adequate counselling and education to dispel misconceptions and address the emotional impact of these diagnoses. Patients require guidance on how to deal with social challenges and avoid stigma. Furthermore, studies have revealed that patients with HBV and HCV experience high rates of anxiety and depression (Fotos et al., 2018; Keskin et al., 2013), which can

aggravate the physical symptoms of the disease. Unfortunately, studies addressing HBV and HCV patients' education and counselling at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital are not included.

Research Question:

- Are you aware of the counselling and education programme for hepatitis B and C patients at Ngwelezane Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa?
- What format of instructions for information dissemination was used for counselling and education in Ngwelezane Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa?
- Were the instructions relevant to your health problems if you were aware of them?

Methodology

This study investigates the role of counselling and education in improving treatment adherence for HBV and HCV patients at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, South Africa. This study was grounded in the idea of interpretivist researchers in collecting qualitative data. Qualitative data is crucial to determine the awareness of HBV and HCV patients regarding counselling and education for patients, as the qualitative approach was used for this study. Qualitative data was collected from HBV and HCV patients receiving treatment at the hospital until data saturation reached eighteen at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, South Africa. A purposive sampling technique was used while data was collected through in-depth interviews with patients who consented and availed themselves of the interview. The data collection procedure involved recruiting participants for qualitative data in Ngwelezane District Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa, between 2020 and 2021. The researchers applied inclusive and exclusive criteria to avoid bias and ensure that only patients suffering from HBV and HCV diseases were recruited for the interview.

The target population was limited to HBV and HCV patients aged eighteen years and above who consented and were willing to provide rich information. Patients eighteen years old and those who declined to participate in the study were excluded. The researchers ensure that the research design adheres to ethical standards as enshrined by the research policy of the University of Zululand, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa (UZREC171110-030PGD2020/8; dated 2/09/2020 and 2021, respectively). The ethical clearances were approved and provided by the committee of Ngwelezane District Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal Province, South Africa, and ethical clearance from the health research and knowledge management unit of the Department of Health, KwaZulu-Natal Province (NHRD REF.KZ-220-004; dated 13/11/2020), South Africa to ensure the compliance of the research practices to the ethical standard.

Despite challenges with data collection due to COVID-19, all COVID-19 protocols and restrictions were observed with patients before interviews with patients within hospital facilities. The signed informed consent was kept in safe custody for future reference. At the same time, the confidentiality policy of patient information use was duly followed. Patients were reassured that non-participation in the interview had no consequences because it was voluntary. They were free to withdraw their participation if they wished. Other participants who declined were excluded. The qualitative data were proofread, organised and interpreted according to the theme of the objectives set for the study and related to the study's theoretical framework.

Results

This section presents the data analysis collected through the participants' interviews. The next section presents the biodata of the participants for the qualitative data collections.

Table 1 illustrates the biodata of the participants for qualitative data collections.

Table 1. The Bio-Data of the Participants for Qualitative Interview

Participants	Participants Per Gender		Economic Status		Age Group	
	Male	Female	Employed	Not Employed		
HBV and HCV Patients	8	10	3	15	20-29	1
					30-39	5
					40-49	6
					50-59	6
Total	8	10	3	15		18

Table 5.2: Participants for the qualitative interview based on purposive sampling.

Table 1 shows the bio-data of the participants using the interview as a means of data collection from the population group. Most participants were female (n=10; 55.6%), and others were male (n=8; 44.4%). Most participants were not employed (n=15; 83.3%), against a few employed (n=3; 16.7%).

On the other hand, the age range of the majority of the participants was between 40 – 49 years (n=12; 66.7%), followed by 30 – 39 (n=5; 28%) and 20 – 29 (n=1; 5.6%). The data collected from HBV and HCV patients were based on awareness of the counselling and education programme organised for hepatitis B and C patients in Ngwelezane Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. The following are the developing themes.

Table 2: Counselling and Education for HBV and HCV Patients

<p>Research Question 1 <i>Are you aware of the counselling and education programme for hepatitis B and C patients at Ngwelezane Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa?</i></p>	<p><i>"I am not aware of any format of information dissemination."</i></p> <p><i>"Yes, I am aware".</i></p>
<p>Research Question 2 <i>What format of instructions for information dissemination was used for counselling and education in Ngwelezane Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa?</i></p>	<p><i>I am aware because I received counselling from health professionals. I received advice from health professionals. I am unaware of a program, but I still receive counselling from doctors and nurses every morning. I am not aware of any format of information dissemination.</i></p> <p><i>Sometimes, the doctors come to give us instructions face to face. I am still determining. I always read information from posters and notice boards in the hospital. I listen to counselling from doctors during my visits. Although I need to learn about the instruction formats, I only listen to doctors' advice during my visits.</i></p> <p><i>Although I am unaware of any program, I always listen to doctor's counselling during my visits. I also read health information on the posters and notice boards in the hospital.</i></p> <p><i>I also listen to information from doctors and nurses during a morning briefing.</i></p>

Research Question 3

Were the instructions relevant to your health problems if you were aware of them?

Yes, the instructions were very relevant to my health needs. I am not sure if they are very relevant to my health needs.

Discussions of Findings

This study explores the experiences of HBV and HCV patients with counselling and education by healthcare professionals regarding knowledge and awareness, the format of instructions, and the relevance of information provision to patients' health problems at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. Based on research question one, the participants were asked, "Are you aware of the counselling and education programme organised for hepatitis B and C patients in Ngwelezane Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa?". Most participants indicated that they do not need counselling and education programmes and the format of information dissemination. However, only a few participants indicated that they were aware.

The World Health Organization (2020:1) has made provisions available for health education and counselling in every tertiary health institution to cater to the physical and mental well-being of patients visiting the facilities. For this study, "health" refers to "the complete physical, mental and social well-being of HBV and HCV patients" and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. Therefore, individuals who wish to enjoy good health must adopt healthy habits as instructed by healthcare providers using guidelines by WHO (2024). The role of counselling and education as strategies for improving health and preventing or managing chronic diseases such as HBV and HCV patients must be considered. According to the *Online Dictionary of Nursing* (2021), "health education" is a "method used to inform people (either individually or collectively), persuade and enable them to

adopt lifestyles that are believed to improve health and reject habits regarded as harmful to health," while counselling is a "method of approaching psychological difficulties in adjustment that aims to help the client work out his problems."

Furthermore, based on research question two, the participants were asked, "What format of instructions for information dissemination were used for counselling and education in Ngwelezane Hospital, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa?" In the responses to the question of what format of instructions for information dissemination they are using, a number of the participants indicated that they need to be made aware of any channel or programmes the hospital uses to disseminate information. At the same time, some said they receive counselling from health professionals and still receive counselling every morning from doctors and nurses.

I am aware because I received counselling from health professionals. I am unaware of a program, but I still receive counselling every morning from doctors and nurses. I am not aware of any format of information dissemination.

Similar findings from related studies (People living with HIV/AIDS) reveal that patients may interact with manual information sources such as computerised systems while looking for information about HIV/AIDS or HBV and HCV risk behaviours. Consequently, individuals may look for information on purpose to achieve a goal, although this action

could be referred to as information seeking, not counselling. On the other hand, some participants revealed that doctors usually come to instruct them face-to-face. In contrast, some participants indicated that they read some information from posters and hospital notice boards, while a few others listened to counselling from doctors during hospital visitations and during morning briefings.

Sometimes, the doctors come to give us instructions face to face. I am still determining. I always read information from posters and notice boards in the hospital. I listen to counselling from doctors during my visits. Although I have yet to learn the instruction format, I only listen to counselling from doctors during my visits. Yes, although I am not aware of any program, I always listen to counselling from doctors during my visits. I read about health information through the posters and notice boards in the hospital. I do not know about any program, but I listen to counselling from doctors during my visits. I also listen to information from doctors and nurses during a morning briefing. I also listen to information from doctors and nurses during the morning briefing.

It is important to note that patients must be counselled or educated using different methods and approaches to either inform or persuade them individually or collectively to adopt lifestyles that will improve their health conditions (Cinar *et al.*, 2015, p. 343). At

times, when seeking information through different sources, accessibility is essential. However, only a few might have equal access to the Internet while seeking information, which is why some consider counselling and education through healthcare providers more reliable. Counselling through healthcare is critical to acquiring the knowledge required to prevent risky actions, eventually enhancing their healthcare and quality of life (Adebayo, 2019).

Based on research question three, the participants were asked *if they were aware of the instructions provided and if they were relevant to their health problems.*

The critical question is whether their instructions are relevant to the patient's health problems. According to related information, HBV and HCV are significant activities in people's lives. Health information must be relevant to the patient's health problems because healthcare professionals must provide accurate diagnosis and treatment (Ball *et al.*, 2015). Since quality of life is essential, health information provided during counselling sessions by healthcare providers needs to be relevant to patients' health needs (Devauraju & Pulikythies (2011).

Yes, the instructions are very relevant to my health needs. They may not be pertinent to my health needs. I am still determining.

Relevant information provides a clearer picture of the health problems at hand, allowing healthcare providers to identify the root cause of the problem (Al-Amer *et al.*, 2015). It can also help doctors tailor treatments directly to the patient's needs; in turn, patients need to understand their health problems to make informed decisions alongside their doctors, leading to better treatment outcomes (Shepherd *et al.*, 2011). A lack of information and understanding at healthcare facilities could result in significant patient problems, such as

physical handicaps, financial loss, and death in the worst-case scenario. According to Kutty, Kumar, Himanshu, and Pathak (2007), such knowledge impacts the direction in which a decision is taken as a choice leading to a specific desired outcome, namely the prevention of harm. Patients must understand their health problems to make informed decisions alongside their doctors. Understanding can lead to full awareness of treatment options, health risks, and potential side effects of medication administered or better treatment outcomes (Hibbard, 2017).

Conclusions

The study established the role of counselling and education in improving treatment adherence for HBV and HCV patients. Regarding receiving counselling and education for awareness by HBV and HCV patients, findings revealed that most patients needed to be made aware of counselling and health education provided on clinic days, only a few participants indicated their awareness of counselling and education during their clinic days. Awareness of essential modes of instruction targeted at improving patients' health is crucial within hospital facilities. The patients also confirmed that doctors' and nurses' formats of information dissemination were direct counselling rather than formal education. Other formats of information provision included posters, pamphlets, group counselling, and magazines. Findings revealed that doctors and nurses counselled patients during consultation and treatment. Most patients know the importance of counselling and health education on HBV and HCV disease prevention and management in the hospital. Counselling and education by the hospital could prepare patients socially and psychologically to cope with the challenges of the treatment received. This study established that patients needed help to determine the relevance of counselling and education by

doctors and nurses. Patients needing special attention could also be referred to psychologists and social workers to help them recover their social and psychological health.

The study was limited to the role of counselling and education for improving treatment adherence for HBV and HCV patients at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, South Africa. Data collections were limited to HBV and HCV patients receiving treatment at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital, South Africa. The researcher may apply findings from this study to another health context in South Africa and sub-Saharan African countries. However, the study's findings were limited to the population at Ngwelezane Tertiary Hospital. The methodological scope was limited to qualitative data collected through in-depth interviews with HBV and HCV patients who consented and availed themselves of the interview. The target population was limited to HBV and HCV patients aged eighteen years and above who consented and were willing to provide rich information. The researcher did not include patients eighteen years old and those who declined to participate in the study. Regarding counselling and education of hepatitis B and C, this study bridged the gap in providing the required methods of counselling patients and education to control the spread of the dangerous but silent disease.

The study's findings have practical implications for healthcare professionals. The study enhances treatment adherence by improving the effectiveness of various methods of information dissemination, such as pamphlets, online resources, and counselling sessions. Understanding information dissemination strategies in various healthcare contexts is essential for improving patient outcomes. Information retrieval is an essential aspect of the information science field. The retrieval of existing literature by the researchers in this context is crucial to identifying counselling and education

interventions previously studied in the context of improving treatment adherence for HBV and HCV patients. They searched relevant literature using information retrieval techniques, such as scoping reviews and database searches, which can contribute to methodologies for effectively accessing and synthesising relevant information. This study contributes to the body of knowledge using health informatics tools such as bibliometric/quantitative content analysis to analyse the existing literature on the topics and technologies to track patient adherence, monitor treatment outcomes, and deliver counselling and education interventions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, this study provides the following recommendations:

- Hepatitis B and C patients will learn about the counselling and education services that the hospital management provides during their visitations.
- Patients are to find out from their doctors, nurses, or other healthcare team members to connect them with the relevant departments.
- Community members must always check hospital websites to look for patient information resources or find out at the information desk.
- Many hospitals have dedicated patient education departments or resource centres. These centres could provide brochures, educational materials, and lists of counselling services available.
- Patients are also advised to contact support groups specific to their health condition or might have information on resources and counselling/education services provided by the hospital or affiliated professionals.
- Patients could also speak to a social worker to help them understand or

connect them with the appropriate counselling and educational support within the hospital system.

- The hospital can organise counselling for disease-specific education for patients and the general public in the form of workshops or individual sessions to help you understand your diagnosis, treatment options, and how to manage your condition.
- Counselling focusing on mental health can be provided to support patients suffering from anxiety, depression, or stress related to their medical condition.
- The hospital could provide community support services for groups and individual counselling to reduce isolation and help patients connect with others who understand what they are going through.

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